

ON SOME TENDENCIES OF DEVELOPING DIVERGENT AND CONVERGENT FEATURES IN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The preceding claims and theories of language development were revised due to a paradigm shift in linguistics. Now, the resurgence of anthropocentric paradigms allowed linguists to view language as a system of symbols used exclusively by humans, and everything pertaining to people and individual speakers became the main focus of linguistic research, which encouraged scholars to consider the essence and history of the homo eloquent.

In the process of forming the norms of pronunciation of the English language, we encounter many divergent features. Scientists have studied the nature of these signs in detail and have also shown the substrate factor as the reason for them. Divergent and convergent features in ancient northern languages. They are the: weakening of syllables at the end of words: short vowels are dropped (syncope), long vowels are shortened; the phenomenon of umlaut in various forms, which occurs as a result of reduction; the phenomenon of the disappearance of the sounds [j] and [w] that come before the back consonants at the beginning of the word in pronunciation (i.e., becoming unreadable); at the end of the word, including the "-n" in the infinitive, is dropped; a number of assimilation cases are observed in consonants; a simplification occurred in the declension of the present tense singular form of verbs; the middle (genitive) form of verbs appeared by receiving the suffixes [-sk, -s]; the definite article, used as a suffix from the postpositive, or rather, the demonstrative pronoun that comes after a noun, developed; new pronouns appeared. [3] Let us consider examples of any language that has not experienced any substrate influence among the currently existing Germanic languages. As such a language, we can only take Faroese. Because when the Germanic tribes went to the Faroe Islands, no one lived there, the Germanic tribes were the first people to settle there. From this point of view, if we do not take into account the substrate influence that the Faroese language received in the pan-Germanic state in Europe and the Scandinavian Peninsula, if such an influence existed, it should have retained this or that language characteristic of all that developed on the islands and not have found any new sources of influence. In practice, in this language we can observe the unstressed pronunciation that is observed in English and French and is considered to be the influence of the Celtic substrate. As for palatalization, Faroese is even more advanced than English. Icelandic also has a similar diphthongization of long vowels. For example: a [au] (on, at, in);

oska [ou:ska] (to want, to wish, to desire); her [hɛ:r] (here). In Icelandic, the diphthongization of the vowels [i:] and [u:] is not observed, as is the case in Faroese. However, these circumstances do not allow us to say that Icelandic is a sign developed under the influence of Celtic languages. [2]

The use of substrate theory in explaining language contacts and language history, various specific features of the language situation, and in explaining and evaluating divergent and convergent features in language development is a very difficult process. Because in a situation where a substrate phenomenon is observed, it is difficult to say whether the primary language of the indigenous population or the second language of the invaders had the dominant features. It is very difficult to determine which languages were responsible and active in the spread of these changes and innovations in the language space, and which changes were caused by them. But even so, in order to find answers to these questions, when studying the history of languages in which divergent or convergent features are found, we need to have a clear idea of their speech stereotypes, carefully study the issue of tolerance of these languages to innovations and the role of socio-political and linguocultural factors that played a major role in ensuring the spread of these innovations in the geopolitical region. Because it would not be correct to say that any divergence and convergence phenomena occur spontaneously, without the influence of non-linguistic external factors, but only on the basis of internal language laws.

Although innovations arise on the basis of the internal structure of the language, the laws of internal development, they need suitable external conditions. If these suitable conditions do not exist, innovations, convergent and divergent signs are doomed to death. This is a situation that has been repeated and repeatedly observed in the history of world languages. Languages, or rather, the speech skills of people speaking those languages, play a major role in studying the emergence and development of divergent and convergent features in a language. Because for a people adapted to a certain articulation, the need to pronounce a sound that does not exist in their language leads to a certain level of tension of the articulatory organs of this speaker. Naturally, the tension is not permanent, it tires the speaker, and his brain begins to look for more free forms of pronunciation without strain.

We have said that divergent and convergent features appear and develop more in situations where there are language contacts. In the process of learning the language of another people, elements of their pronunciation norms are introduced, and these atavistic (a sign or organ that has survived unchanged from the primitive periods of evolution) features remain in the language for a certain time. For these atavistic features to disappear, one or two generations of change are required..

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